

ROTATOR CUFF INJURY AND SHOULDER INSTABILITY: OUR CLINICAL CASE WITH SURGICAL TREATMENT IN A TEENAGER**Saliev S.M.***MSc, Researcher of the Department of Arthroscopy,
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Medical Center of Traumatology and Orthopedics, Tashkent***Abstract**

Background: The Latarjet procedure can improve anterior stability through several mechanisms, not only can the Bankart lesion be cured and provide stability, but the transfer of the coracoid process expands the bony articular arch of the glenoid, and the addition of a connected tendon can provide dynamic stability.

Case presentation: We present the case of a 15-year-old male teenager with an unstable shoulder who was unable to raise his left arm due to pain. In the 2 years prior to the onset of pain, the patient could asymptotically perform voluntary subluxation, but it was minor and the direction of the subluxation could not be confirmed. On physical examination, the load-and-shift test, the sulcus test, and the anterior apprehension test were positive for assessing the shoulder. MRI and MSCT studies showed Bankart's bone lesion. There was no posterior Bankart lesion. Due to painful instability of the anterior part of the shoulder, an open Latarjet procedure was performed.

After the operation, the patient was in a sling for the first 4 weeks after the operation. During this initial period, the patient is allowed to perform mild passive, active, and active movements of the shoulder in the scapular plane. In addition, resistance elbow flexion was prohibited for at least the first 6 weeks after surgery. After a period of bone healing, active rehabilitation exercises were allowed according to the protocol (Helen Bradley et al., 2021). Return to contact sports or heavy work activities was not allowed 5 months after surgery.

Conclusion: The Latarjet procedure to correct recurrent anterior dislocation of the shoulder gives good results in the literature in 82.7% of cases. The open Latarjet procedure is effective in restoring anterior-inferior shoulder joint stability and is a good option for failed arthroscopic Bankart repair. The recurrence rate of instability was acceptable and the reoperation rate was low. The author group considered that the Latarjet arthroscopic procedure resulted in satisfactory radiographic and clinical results for the treatment of patients with recurrent anterior shoulder instability and significant glenoid bone loss along with an open approach. The choice of tactics depends on the experience of the surgeon, and an important role in a good result depends on the appropriate rehabilitation treatment.

Keywords: shoulder instability, Latarjet procedure, bony Bankart

Background: Anterior shoulder instability is frequently seen condition, especially in younger patients. Conservative management of shoulder instability was related with much number of recurrence incidence between 37% to 85% (Hovelius L. et al., 2008, DeBernardino T. et al., 1996, Roberts S., 2005).

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was unable to raise his left arm due to pain. In the 2 years prior to the onset of pain, the patient could asymptotically perform voluntary subluxation, but it was minor and the direction of the subluxation could not be confirmed. On physical examination, the load-and-shift test, the sulcus test, and the anterior apprehension test were positive for assessing the shoulder. MRI and MSCT studies showed Bankart's bone lesion. There was no posterior Bankart lesion. Due to painful instability of the anterior part of the shoulder, an open Latarjet procedure was performed.

Picture 1: MSCT before operation

Picture: X ray after 6 months of follow up. AP View.

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Picture X: Apprehension test PostOP 6 months

Picture X: MSCT scan of the shoulder PostOP 6 months

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Discussion and conclusion: The Latarjet procedure to correct recurrent anterior dislocation of the shoulder gives good results in the literature in 82.7% of cases. The open Latarjet procedure is effective in restoring anterior-inferior shoulder joint stability and is a good option for failed arthroscopic Bankart repair. The recurrence rate of instability was acceptable and the reoperation rate was low. The author group considered that the Latarjet arthroscopic procedure resulted in satisfactory radiographic and clinical results for the treat-

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References

1. Hovelius L., Olofsson A., Sandstrom B. Nonoperative treatment of primary anterior shoulder dislocation in patients forty years of age and younger. a prospective twenty-five-year follow-up. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 2008;90:945–952.
2. DeBerardino T.M., Arciero R.A., Taylor D.C. Arthroscopic stabilization of acute initial anterior shoulder dislocation: The West Point experience. *J South Orthop Assoc.* 1996;5:263–271.
3. Roberts S.B., Beattie N., McNiven N.D., Robinson C.M. The natural history of primary anterior dislocation of the glenohumeral joint in adolescence. *J Bone Joint Br.* 2015;97:520–526.